

PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS FOR FORMING SOCIAL CREATIVITY IN FUTURE EDUCATIONAL MANAGERS

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of improving the organizational and management mechanisms for the formation of social creativity in future educational managers and the tasks of forming social creativity in future educational managers are studied based on advanced foreign experiences. Also, theoretical aspects of the formation of social creativity in future educational managers were analyzed.

Key words: principle, mechanism, improvement, theoretical-methodological basis, international standards, academic, marketing, management, integration, forecasting, globalization, functional, manager, social creativity, modernization, authoritarian, liberal-democratic, scientific-organizational, conceptual-pedagogical, hierarchical.

INTRODUCTION. When discussing creative thinking, this often refers to internal determinism. Internal deterministic factors include abilities, inspiration, the drive to think and create, the desire to change and beautify the environment, and the ideal formed in the mind, among other creative psychological phenomena. These phenomena, especially in the minds of young people, play a leading role in their lives. 82% of our respondents evaluate the interest of our President and government in the youth's engagement with innovation and creative research as a positive reality and express their intention to make use of these opportunities. 78% of them state that educational institutions such as schools, universities, and family require the youth to develop into creative individuals, and that parents play a crucial role in this process. They highlight that the spiritual and moral atmosphere in the family, noble qualities, mutual help, altruism, respect for the elderly, and reverence for the young create a supportive and encouraging environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS. The theoretical and methodological foundations for improving the organizational and managerial mechanisms for developing social creativity in future educational managers have been studied and analyzed by Ph. Altbach, K.A. Khoon, R. Shukor, O. Hassan, Z. Saleh, A. Hamzah, R. Ismail, N.V. Demidova, S.V. Sulima, S.A. Drujilov, K.I.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Specialists emphasize that the human brain has the capacity to process information equivalent to 35 km of storage space. Wunderkinds who can memorize an entire text after reading it once, write with both hands simultaneously, and recall up to thirty numbers in sequence are abundant. This suggests that anyone, particularly the youth, can be trained to engage in any form of creative activity. Modern education and pedagogy are based on this principle, as confirmed by the responses of our respondents.

Training creative, innovative youths capable of developing new technologies requires a new pedagogical approach and education model. Without addressing this issue, the training of scientific and technical personnel would deepen the ongoing crises. In the West, exemplary research has been conducted, with scientific centers for studying global crises and technical expertise institutions being established. Between 1945 and 2000, nearly 400 universities and academies that trained globally-minded, highly educated scientific and technical personnel were opened across Europe. The policy of humanizing scientific and technological discoveries, i.e., supporting innovations that align with humanity's ultimate goals, was implemented. Changes in social life are not easy; social thinking has a contradictory formation process. One should not draw a palliative conclusion that, as a result of the President's efforts, decrees, and decisions, no problems remain in life and that our youth are living happy lives. Youth, like social life itself, continuously presents new challenges for the state and demands the advancement of society.

Because a person is not a being who is content with stagnation and absolute life, but rather one who, as Eastern wisdom emphasizes, seeks to see a "perfect world" and desires to see themselves as developed and elevated. A person's inclination to know, understand, create something, and search for the secrets of the world makes them dissatisfied with life's meaning. The shortcomings in social life are even acknowledged by our country's leadership. As the President says, "There are still shortcomings in working with youth. In particular, the Youth Union, which was established with grand objectives, is not

paying enough attention to working systematically with youth and addressing their problems.”

Today, modern education is placing special emphasis on discovering students' creative abilities. Through this, identifying their inner talents and directing them towards professional activities is proving to be effective. The educational process aims to realize and develop a student's natural talent according to their individual characteristics, ultimately fostering a well-rounded personality. It is impossible to forcefully teach something without identifying the student's inherent talent. If their innate ability is more developed than others, it provides them with the opportunity to make a discovery. Therefore, discovering and creating opportunities for students' creative abilities to develop remains one of the most pressing tasks.

Training future educational managers to think freely and deliver lessons using new technologies and methods not only helps form knowledge and skills but also nurtures creativity and innovative abilities. In life, boys and girls with high potential have achieved more perfection and satisfaction with their efforts compared to those who are merely original thinkers. "Parents and teachers usually place more trust in idea developers, and these children fear disappointing them. Original thinkers, especially girls, set high goals for themselves, and teachers and parents, in turn, often do not have high hopes for their future."

Original thinkers prefer a competitive approach in interpersonal relationships, while idea developers prefer collaboration. The essence of creative abilities lies in the psychological foundations of heuristic education, which are the personal qualities of a person that determine and cause their effective educational activity. Analyzing the works of psychologists and educators in this field helps identify the psychological and pedagogical directions for expressing students' creativity.

Philosophers believe that creativity is the true essence of a subject, both internally and externally related to the world. Creativity, high creativity, does not occur without the subjective participation of the individual and is realized only through the unique characteristics of the creative person. In pedagogy, creativity is primarily understood as invention, originality, imagination, sensitivity, and the ability to solve problems quickly. It is emphasized that creativity is multi-dimensional. Creativity is the potential capacity for comprehensive thinking, feeling, and acting. "It is the ability to approach problematic situations and find a way out of them creatively." Creativity can be

defined as striving for creation, approaching life with creativity, and constantly engaging in self-criticism and analysis. Based on current psychological and pedagogical definitions, the creativity of a teacher can be defined as their creative approach to thinking, communication, and a particular activity type. This involves originality, practicality, unusualness, and freedom. Creative thinking also means approaching an issue from different angles. Every person is born with creative potential. The task of the teacher is to guide and develop this potential.

Therefore, in all types of education in schools, focusing on the development of students' creative abilities serves as the foundation for nurturing a well-rounded generation. In pedagogy, creativity is understood as a person's "ability to create" and is analyzed in relation to the development of intellect. For example, A. Arifjanova describes the essence of creativity in terms of developing the creative potential of higher education faculty members: "Through mobilizing the right opportunities, the ability of an individual to accept problems and create new, unconventional products." According to G. Ibragimova, creativity is manifested as a set of skills associated with a person's creative and inventive qualities. Creativity encompasses a high degree of sensitivity to problems, intuition, the ability to foresee outcomes, imagination, research, and reflection.

In our view, creativity is an integrative ability that encompasses interrelated abilities and elements. For example, creative abilities include imagination, fantasy, dreaming, and the development of unique talents. Creativity is a fundamental, though not the only, ability that ensures heuristic cognitive activity. As a result of creative and instrumental activities in students, the cognitive process certainly takes place. In this process, creative and cognitive activities occur together. To express these creative and cognitive processes, which share a common structural basis, an organizational and methodological activity appropriate to the student's abilities is necessary.

Moreover, a person's creativity is manifested in their thinking, communication, emotions, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or certain aspects of their personality. It also reflects talent as an essential factor. Furthermore, creativity defines mental sharpness. Clearly, creativity is directly related to the individual-psychological characteristics of a person. Its development occurs under the influence of intellect, intuition, and logical thinking processes.

Organizational abilities include goal-setting, striving for goals, the ability to plan work, adherence to established standards, self-awareness, and others.

An essential condition for organizing creativity is assertiveness (from the Latin *assertorius* – to affirm, to assert). This refers to the ability to perform a particular type of work based on one's own understanding. Assertiveness means the manifestation of a person's unique qualities.

Heuristic education relies on three integrative abilities for student development: creative, cognitive, and organizational activities.

Conclusion. Heuristic education refers to the complex possibilities of student activities and actions aimed at creating products. Creativity is understood as "the process of deeply understanding the ability of individuals to generate unique ideas and make innovative decisions." Today, the main requirement for education is the development of a creative personality capable of making non-standard decisions, going beyond set boundaries, and creating products that stand out with innovation. Psychologists refer to creativity in terms of the problem of ability and often perceive it as general creative ability, the process of changing knowledge. Furthermore, they emphasize that creativity is associated with the development of imagination and the formulation of hypotheses. Creative abilities are classified in various ways. Based on research on creative or innovative abilities, it can be recognized that different amounts and contents of personality traits emerge in various students.

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